

Reactions of certain rice cultivars to sheath rot disease

S. Kannaiyan, V. Jayaraman, and V. G. Palaniyandi, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram-627401, Tamil Nadu, India

A field trial in the 1977 kar season (July–October) observed the reactions of 130 rice cultivars to sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* by natural infection at earhead maturity stage. Six of the rices were completely disease free (see table) and 18 were relatively resistant, with disease incidence ranging from 2.4 to 20.0%. AS 5127 showed the maximum disease incidence (89%). The incidence in the rest of the cultivars ranged from 0 to 20%. **W**

Reaction of rice varieties to sheath rot disease. Tamil Nadu state, India.

Rice cultivar	Disease incidence (%)
AS 5821	0
AS 6975	0
AS 2992	0
Cult. 1287	0
Cult. 3226	0
Cult. 6403	0
Cult. 2692	2
AS 2572	3
Cult. 643	4
AD 5983	5
AS 2522	7
AS 5277	8
CRM 95-15-12-4	8
AS 5250	9
CR95-721-3	10
AS 6479	12
CR15-7-392-11-4	13
Cult. 1145	14
AS 2444	14
AS 2887	15
AD 6148	15
AD 608	19
AS 4417	19
CR 94-214	20
AS 5127	89

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Evaluation of the 1977 International Rice Stem Borer Nursery at IRRI

E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist, and L. Malabuyoc, and C. Vega, research assistants, International Rice Research Institute

The International Rice Stem Borer Nursery (IRSBN) of the International Rice Testing Program was first conducted in 1976. The 1977 IRSBN consists of 83 entries submitted by rice scientists from 4 countries. Seed sets have been sent to 10 countries.

At IRRI, the 1977 IRSBN was evaluated against the striped borer *Chilo suppressalis* and the yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*. For the striped borer test, two replicates of two rows, each consisting of 20 hills, were planted. The IRSBN was infested by allowing adults reared from larvae and from eggs that had been placed on an early planted, susceptible variety to oviposit on the test entries. Deadhearts were counted at 60 days after transplanting (DT). In the

yellow borer test, three replicates of 2 rows, each consisting of 20 plants, were transplanted. At 30 DT 5 newly hatched larvae were placed on each plant with a camel's hair brush. At 75 DT deadhearts were counted.

No entry had a high level of resistance. Several entries had intermediate resistance to one of the stem borer species but only a few had intermediate resistance to both (see table). Entries showing the most resistance had about 50% fewer deadhearts than the susceptible check. The lines IET 2845, IET 5540, and IRI 820-52-2 also had intermediate levels of resistance against the stem borer population, which was predominantly *Chilo polychrysus* in the 1976 IRSBN planted in Thailand.

No entry in the yellow borer test was significantly more resistant than the resistant check IR1820-52-2. A few lines in the striped borer test were only slightly better than the resistant check W1263. Thus, no sources with high levels of resistance to the two stem borers are

Entries in the 1977 IRSBN that had intermediate levels of resistance against both *Tryporyza incertulas* and *Chilo suppressalis*. IRRI greenhouse, 1977.

IRTP entry no.	Designation	Cross	Deadhearts (%)	
			<i>T. incertulas</i> 75DT ^a	<i>C. suppressalis</i> 60 DT
10	IET 2845	TKM6/IR8	23	32
26	IET 5540	IR22/NP30	20	36
33	IR1514 A-E666	IR20/TKM6	19	29
36	IR2328-491-1-1-1	IR8//IR8/Dawn//IR8/KAK/4/K8 Mut.	20	35
38	IR2798-143-3-2	IR1529-680/IR1913-41/IR1514 A-E666	21	36
47	IR4791-89	IR3342/IR3341	21	30
55	IR5201-122-2	IR1820-52-2/IR2061464-2	18	35
65	CR157-392-4	Vijaya/Ptb 10	20	37
72	IR3941-97-1	CR126-42-5/IR2061-213	17	31
75	IR36	IR1561//IR24/ <i>Oryza nivara</i> ///CR94-13	19	35
	Resistant checks			
	IR1820-52-2	IR1539-60/IR1416-128-5-19	19	
	W 1263			45
	Susceptible check			
	Rexoro		52	72

^aDays after transplanting.